

EFFECTIVENESS OF DIGITAL MARKETING TO ONLINE FOOD SELLERS

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Abstract: Aspiring business owners now have a variety of chances to launch businesses with minimal entry barriers and high growth potential thanks to the rise of digital entrepreneurship. In today's constantly changing digital environment, digital entrepreneurs can succeed by combining the correct amounts of innovation, technology, and consumer focus. The study's primary objective is to see how effective digital marketing for online food sellers. The researched study employed a descriptive survey method, with qualitative and quantitative designs used to analyze the result of the online survey respectively. Toward the end, the research will be driven by the potential impact of strategic digital marketing what to do and focus in the specific parts of digital marketing.

Keywords: Digital Marketing, Online, Entrepreneurs, Social Media.

I. INTRODUCTION

Young entrepreneurs today are increasing as the pandemic continues. From simple food carts to a complex food business. Becoming a young entrepreneur during a pandemic is one of the best ways to earn not only to sustain needs but also to have extra financial resources. The emergence of many young and successful entrepreneurs' augurs well not only for the nation but for the future of the youths whose exploits will certainly revolutionize the lives of many. But being an entrepreneur demands consideration for a lot of things, including the marketing strategies for the product or services being sold. As bold as one can be, in a time of crisis where people are told to stay home, entrepreneurs must be creative on how they market and promote the products and services they are selling. In comes digital marketing. Advertisements done on social media are hard to miss. Online promotions are easily personalized to cater the wants and needs of the target market a business is aiming for. A well-planned execution of digital marketing may reach just about anyone who's a member of the online community. Social media presence for businesses is far more important in today's world than it was before.

More so, advertisements done online can also be of convenience not just to the business owner, but also to their respective clients. Much like promoting and selling for entrepreneurs, inquiring and purchasing for consumers has never been this easy. Young entrepreneurs are digitally inclined and have mastered the art of social media, so introducing E-marketing to these budding businessmen and businesswomen, is a no-brainer. In a generation so attached to the world wide web, one must maximize the various services and features it offers. Through the use of the world wide web, marketing has become easier for young entrepreneurs today, Advertising can be done online through websites and social media platforms.

It comes with certain limitations that may be a complication for some of the entrepreneurs especially without sufficient knowledge in the innovation of the technological world, precisely:

- a.) Dependability on technology
- b.) Security and Privacy issues
- c.) Maintenance cost due to constantly evolving surroundings.

Regardless of the limitations stated, digital marketing continues to evolve rapidly. This is proven by the intense use of internet marketing and promotions by companies around the world. (Minculete & Olar, 2018)

In the Philippines, social media marketing is being utilized by small business entrepreneurs as it generously provides a free advertisement for their products even though the concept of digital marketing offers a range of challenges in the Philippines. In a written article, (Lee-del Rosario, 2019) stated four challenges of digital marketing. First, consumers have become flexible to access more than ever before. Second, the clients' journey is how marketing campaign facilitates the consumer's awareness of new products leading them to acquire and utilize them. Third, customers imagine having an improved experience to be unique and consistent to ensure that from product preference to the mode of delivery are worth paying for. Lastly, digital-based marketing should be able to accomplish basic deliverables such as retaining existing customers and increase of sales.

Cybercrime Prevention Act or the Republic Act 10175 is a law of the Philippines that are pertinent or concerning to digital marketing as the cyber prevention act includes the "Unsolicited Commercial Communication" indicating that the transmission of commercial with the use of a computer system which seeks to advertise, sell or offer something for sale is prohibited unless:

- a.) There is prior affirmative consent from the recipient; or
- b.) The primary intent of the communication is for service and/or administrative announcement from the sender to its existing users, subscriber or customers; or
- c.) The following conditions are present:
 - a. The Commercial electronic communication contains a simple, valid and reliable way for the recipient to reject the receipt of further commercial electronic messages (opt-out) from the same source;
 - b. The commercial electronic communication does not purposely disguise the source of the electronic message; and
 - c. The commercial electronic communication does not purposely include misleading information in any part of the message in order to induce the recipient to read the message.

(Republic act no. 10175: Govph. 2012, September 12)

Although the Republic Act 10175 or the Cybercrime Prevention Act presents its conditions, the digital marketing strategy in the Philippines is still possible through abiding by the law mandated by the Supreme Court specifically the Cybercrime Prevention Act.

A. Theoretical Framework

The research study's mission is to foster dissemination of knowledge among e-commerce and online selling industries in order to advance strategic opportunities. This research will enable the online sellers to conduct more in-depth analyses of digital marketing that will be beneficial into the field of online entrepreneurs and consumers.

Going Digital. Merchandising the product is no longer limited to physical stores. The Internet gives customers the information of the product that the entrepreneur is selling. Offering information through a website about the products, its special offering, display and also its price is another way to merchandise the brand and product (Wagner, 2020).

Strategic Digital Marketing. Digital marketing includes all strategies that will reach all the target audiences. This also partakes online marketing methods, email and direct message marketing to reach people on their devices through online advertisements, video streams, and social media announcements (Murrow, 2020).

Target Market and Customer. According to Belcher (2020), potential customers are defined by ranges. The target market needs to have a specific target customer. From the target customers' components, this might also include specific age instead of a range because there's a specific income level versus the large swath of income types.

Methods of Digital Marketing. Marketing in terms of methods may overlap in trying to reach out to the target market versus the target customer. Direct mail is one of the main marketing methods by targeting a certain zip code but also at the same time its a target market in terms of demographic area and online advertisement (Belcher, 2020).

Considerations on Online Marketing Plan. Consideration follows the principles of developing the business situation and understanding what's working and not functioning. Also, prioritizing and setting digital goals that will make a difference

in the online business. Lastly, knowing the target market and customers will largely direct the choices of the entrepreneurs on which digital platform is more effective, active and how it will proceed (Tania, 2020).

B. Conceptual Framework

Figure #1: Conceptual Framework

The diagram above shows the factors of the respondents' assessment of the digital marketing strategy regarding the Product, Price, Place, and Promotion. These factors will help the study to identify the strategies used by the Online Food Sellers and propose an enhanced digital marketing strategy that may help the budding entrepreneurs.

The researchers will conduct an online survey to the clients of Online Food Sellers. The researchers will use purposive and Convenience sampling. The respondents will answer an online survey made by the researchers.

C. Background of the Study

As the pandemic continues, online businesses are increasing like the businesses whose owners agreed to participate to the study with the researchers. With ages ranging from 21 to 30 years old. 385 clients of the Online Food Sellers that have agreed to be part of the research. Being said, the researchers ended up conducting a study regarding digital marketing strategies of young entrepreneurs consider in the era of constant innovation in the marketing world. The business owners who agreed to participate to the study much like everyone follow trends regarding modern-day marketing. The researchers aim to gather information on what digital marketing strategies of Online Food Sellers are executing. The researchers have gained interest in the digital marketing strategy the modern marketing world has that would be of help to online sellers. Digital marketing has become important in today's competitive business world. Different entrepreneurs think of a way how to practically and effectively compete with other entrepreneurs. Gathering the assessment of the clients of new entrepreneurs regarding product, price, place, and promotion will provide researchers digital marketing strategies that will attract relevant target customers.

Statement of the Problem

The study aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 1. Age
 2. Gender
 3. Place of Business
 4. Nature of Business
2. How do the respondents assess the digital marketing strategies of Online Food Sellers in terms of:
 - a. Accuracy of digital advertisements

- b. Frequency of digital advertisements
 - c. Feedbacks from previous customers
 - d. Online Recommendation from previous customers
 - e. Popularity of digital advertisements or pages
3. Is there a significant difference between the rating of respondents on the effectiveness of Digital marketing when grouped according to age and nature of business?
4. Based on the respondent's assessments, what enhanced digital marketing strategy for Online Food Sellers can be proposed.

D. Hypothesis

There is no significant difference between rating of respondents on the effectiveness of Digital marketing when grouped according to age and nature of business.

E. Significance of the Study

The researchers believes that this study will not only yield data that will be helpful but also will be beneficial to the following groups of people:

Online Food Sellers/Food Companies. It will greatly benefit them considerably in terms of the suggested strategic online marketing plan of the researchers' study.

Online Customers. They will learn and be much more aware of how the online business is operating.

Government Officials and Agencies. The study will serve as a valuable resource for conducting assessment, studies, and guidelines in expanding research to enhance the existing laws for protection in online traders and business , especially to the customers.

Educational Institutions/Future Researchers. It will also serve as a reference and guide for future researchers interested in conducting similar or related studies.

F. Scope and Limitations of the Study

This study will focus on the digital marketing strategies used by the Online Food Sellers as business owners and its customers. This will be measured by the respondent's assessments on digital marketing strategy. The researchers will limit the respondents to 385 clients of the Online Food Sellers as they are the majority type of business who agreed to be part of the study.

For this analysis, an online survey method from Google forms will be used as the principal data collection tool. Researchers will be using a descriptive method, mixed with an online qualitative and quantitative research survey.

G. Definition of terms

Entrepreneurs- A person who is starting a new business venture

Google forms - is an approach to create online forms.

Digital Marketing - promotes and sells products through email, social media and advertisements.

Online Food Sellers - allows the business to accept and manage orders placed online for delivery or takeaway.

E-marketing - the marketing of goods and services through the internet

Advertisements - means of communication in which a product, brand or service is promoted to a viewership in order to attract

Technology - a body of knowledge used to create tools, process things, and extract materials.

World wide web - all websites that users can access on their local computers and other devices through the use of the internet.

Commercial electronic communication - any electronic message sent to emails, texts and calls are considered electronic communication, regardless of whether there is an expectation of profit.

ROI - Return On Investment

Social Media Platform - These are the ones we use to connect with other people such as Facebook, Instagram and Twitter.

Google Ads - An online platform used to create their own online advertisements

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This part includes the articles, ideas, and others. Those that are indicated in this part helps to provide information related to the present research.

Understanding Digital Marketing accomplishes well the difficult feat of assembling current practical strategies from leading business owners in the digital marketing field, Marketing is rapidly changing.

Online Technology continues to progress and change all the time. The same idea can be applied to digital marketing. Some platforms or websites today can work in a common smartphone but will not tomorrow. Big changes might happen overnight and the created digital marketing for a business will become a waste. But, that's not the only thing you might face when having E-marketing for a business. Here are

Technology and digital marketing strategies are always changing. As early-stage startups and entrepreneurs are looking to get the pre-product market fit right, they should not consider product development to be more important than branding and digital marketing.

The benefits of digital marketing, Digital marketing is essential in Online business. According to (Assemblo, 2020) digital marketing offers wide brand exposure, cost-effective, targeted, reaches people at every stage of the buying cycle, provides trackable and measurable results.

(Ashraf, 2020) stated that the main advantage of digital marketing is that the target market can be reached in a cost-effective and measurable way.

More advantages of digital marketing is that a social media or website allows one to find new markets and trade all over the world for only a small investment, digital marketing also lower cost, digital marketing campaigns can reach the right target market at much lower cost than traditional marketing methods (Ashraf, (2020). And if they have a social media page or website then they're possible customers are only a few clicks away from making a purchase.

(Weber, 2018) cited that when potential clients ask about the disadvantages of digital marketing, they are tempting to say that there is aren't any. Yet, as with the product and service, there are. digital marketing isn't infallible. Since every company in earth is engage in digital marketing at this point. It's often very difficult for a new business to make a bloom in their field. Certain industries are notoriously competitive.

There are 8 common challenges in the Digital Marketing world. First is "Not Getting lost in Volume" meaning, how to make your digital marketing will stand out among other digital marketing on the internet. Second, "Driving relevant traffic to the website", some entrepreneurs are lost how to reach the right target market. The third is "Targeting the right audience effectively" Fourth, "Lead Generation using social media" when it comes to social media, most entrepreneurs don't know how to remain consistent in it. Most of them feel that it is all about paid advertisements. Followed by the fifth challenge which is "Optimizing marketing budgets and ROI". Sixth, "keeping up with the changing trends". Seventh, "A Check on Increased Security Risks" and lastly, "Lesser Focus on Keywords". (Ahmad, 2016)

Customers are the most precious asset of a firm. Hence, estimating and understanding the economic value of customers is one of the important issues in devising effective marketing strategies. (Baidya et al., 2019)

One of the important aspects to keep in mind for a successful business is branding. As more people have resorted to online marketing in light of the current situation, these key questions can help establish a business' unique identity in the market. As reiterated by (Appleroth, 2015) in her Marketing Plan for A Restaurant, there are six factors in the process: Is it memorable? Meaningful? Likable? Transferable? Adaptable? And lastly, is it worth protecting? These factors will also provide the study reinforcement to gather enough information for the objectives the researchers are aiming at.

According to (Digital Restaurant, n.d.) This are the Frequently asked questions of Business Owners to digital marketing of food service:

- Can they present their own menu and food branding with Digital Marketing site?
- Can they create separate information pages on telling customers about their background, location, hours, etc.?
- Who owns the data of their website?
- Is their website being secure?
- How can they drive their customers in their website or social media page?
- How will digital marketing increase order average through online ordering?

Social media usage and engagement is up since the lock-down began (increases are as high as 61% in some studies) which means the restaurant's social channels are a great opportunity to communicate to the loyal customers and entice new guests to try the food. But re-opening the restaurant doesn't mean re-starting the social media accounts and posting similar content that worked well before coronavirus. (Cialfi, 2020)

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Method / Design

The researchers will use quantitative research, quantitative research approaches emphasize objective measurements and statistical, analytical, or numerical analysis of data gathered by the online survey questionnaire from google forms.

The researchers will use a descriptive research method. Descriptive research design aims to define the factors of the assessment of the respondent regarding the digital marketing strategies of Online Food Sellers. (McCombes, 2019)

B. Population and Sampling

The respondents of the study will be gathered using a purposive and convenience sampling method. In this method, it accesses a particular subset of people, as all respondents of a study are selected because they fit a particular profile (Crossman, 2020). Quota sampling is a method of sampling in which data is obtained from a homogeneous population.

Convenience sampling is a type of nonprobability sampling in which people are sampled simply because they are "convenient" sources of data for researchers. In probability sampling, each element in the population has a known nonzero chance of being selected through the use of a random selection procedure. (Lavrakas, 2008)

Additionally, crowdsourcing will also be used to complete the aimed number of respondents through Facebook post. Crowdsourcing is a source model to obtain information through social media application (Hargrave, 2020).

The researchers will use Krejcie and Morgan formula in determining the number of the respondents required in the study

The sample size (n) is calculated according to the formula: $n = z^2 * p * (1 - p) / e^2$

Where: z = 1.96 for a confidence level (α) of 95%, p = proportion (expressed as a decimal), e = margin of error.

$$\begin{aligned} z &= 1.96, & p &= 0.5, & e &= 0.05 \\ n &= 1.962 * 0.5 * (1 - 0.5) / 0.052 \\ n &= 0.9604 / 0.0025 = 384.16 \\ n &\approx 385 \end{aligned}$$

The sample size is equal to 385

C. Profile of the Respondents

For the profile of the respondents, the study will gather data from the clients of Online Food Sellers with ages between 18 to 45 years old and above. The majority of business types who agreed as part of the study, the researchers are aiming for

the clients of Online Food Sellers in Region IV-A CALABARZON and NCR region as it will be easy for the researchers to visit the businesses if necessary.

D. Research Instrument

This study will conduct an online survey using Google Forms. Due to the pandemic, the respondents of this study consist of the clients of Online Food Sellers.

The 4-Point Likert scale will be used in answering the online survey questionnaire for the statement of problem number 2 of the study.

E. Data Gathering Procedure

An online survey method using google forms will be used as the main data-gathering instrument for this study. With this, a quantitative research online survey will be used. Survey questionnaires are the most common method for quantitative research data collection. With online survey questionnaires, resources have advanced features increasingly available, more researchers are embracing web-based survey selection for a quantitative study.

In the online survey questionnaire, the respondents will be informed of the intent of the study and will be asked if they meet the predefined requirements of the researchers. The respondents will also be asked if they are willing to answer the survey questionnaire and the approval to grant the researchers for conducting the analysis. The online survey questionnaire will take 5-10 minutes and will be collected using Google forms with the consent of the respondents for documentation purposes. Also, 4-Point Likers scale will be used in the questionnaire to answer the statement of problem number 2 specifically; "How do the respondents assess the digital marketing strategies of Online Food Sellers during the pandemic".

The data collected from the respondents will be then analyzed and interpreted after using Statistics.

F. SData Treatment and Analysis

The proponents will use weighted mean and percentage in gathering data, which will then be interpreted. The weighted mean will enable the researchers to determine the assessment status of the Online Food Sellers. The assessment and the respondents' demographic profile percentage will then be tabulated from the data obtained from the collected questionnaires.

Weighted mean formula:

$$W = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i X_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i}$$

Where:

W = weighted average

n = number of terms to be averaged

w_i = weights applied to x values

X_i = data values to be averaged

Percentage formula:

$$\% = \frac{f}{N} \times 100$$

Where:

$\%$ = percent

f = frequency

N = number of respondents

For the analysis of the survey, Statistical treatment will be used. Statistical treatment describes the relationship between variables in a population, or inferential statistics, which tests a hypothesis by making inferences from the collected data. (DiscoverPhDs, 2020)

ANOVA will also be used for the treatment to show the difference between two or more means, it is also used in making multiple comparisons of several means. (Byjus.com, 2020)

F = MST/MSE

MST = SST/ p-1

MSE = SSE/N-p

SSE = $\sum (n-1) s^2$

Where:

F = Anova Coefficient

MSB = Mean sum of squares between the groups

MSW = Mean sum of squares within the groups

MSE = Mean sum of squares due to error

SST = total Sum of squares

p = Total number of populations

n = The total number of samples in a population

SSW = Sum of squares within the groups

SSB = Sum of squares between the groups

SSE = Sum of squares due to error

s = Standard deviation of the samples

N = Total number of observations

Chi Square will also be used as the chi square distribution is the distribution of the sum of these random samples squared. The degrees of freedom (k) are equal to the number of samples being summed. (Eck & Ryan, n.d.)

$$\chi_c^2 = \sum \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i}$$

Where:

For the repeated values, frequency formula will be used.

Where:

$$f_i = \frac{f}{n}$$

The data was interpreted in terms of criteria based on the following scales.

Interval	Level of Agreement/ Disagreement	Interpretation
1.00 - 1.49	Strongly disagree	Very Poor
1.50 - 2.49	Disagree	Poor
2.50 - 3.49	Agree	Good
3.50 - 4.00	Strongly agree	Very Good

IV. PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

The primary purpose of this study is to determine and analyze the common problems encountered by the research while conducting their investigation.

This chapter summarizes the data acquired, analyzes it, and interprets the conclusions based on the results of the statistical treatment used. The data are categorized chronologically according to the research questions posed.

1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

The demographic characteristics of the respondents are summarized in Tables 1 to 4. They include their age, gender, number of years in the business, place of business, and nature of business. Within the study's reach, the researcher picked 385 respondents particularly Online Food Sellers in Region IV-A and NCR.

TABLE 1: Frequency Distribution and Percentage of Respondents According to Age

Age Range	Frequency	Percentage
20 years old and below	32	8.3%
21 - 30 years old	241	62.6%
31 - 40 years old	86	22.3%
41 - 50 years old	24	6.2%
51 years old and above	2	0.5%
Total	385	100%

Based on the data above, it can be seen that 62.6% of the respondents came from the 21 - 30 age bracket. It was followed by 22.3% of the respondents who belong to the 31-40 age bracket. 8.3% of the respondents came from the 20 years old and below age bracket. Next is 6.2% from the 41 - 50 age bracket. Finally, the least number of respondents came from the 51 years of age and above bracket. This is expected since the majority of the respondents of this study are those who are working within the jurisdiction of the study.

TABLE 2: Frequency Distribution and Percentage of Respondents According to Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	129	33.5%
Female	256	66.5%
Total	385	100%

Based on the data above, it can be seen that there is a greater number of female respondents than males. Females respondents account for 66.5% of the total number of respondents. While male respondents account for only 33.5% of the total number of respondents.

TABLE 3: Frequency Distribution and Percentage of Respondents According to Place of Business

Location	Frequency	Percentage
Region IV-A CALABARZON	230	59.7%
NCR Region	155	40.3%
Total	385	100%

Based on the results available above, it can be gleaned that most of the respondents came from the Region IV-A CALABARZON region. The researcher tried to get respondents who reside in areas near the region and latter was able to secure the total number of respondents from those who came from places in the NCR region.

TABLE 4: Frequency Distribution and Percentage of Respondents According to Nature of Business

Nature of Business	Frequency	Percentage
Food only	160	41.6%
Drinks only	76	19.7%
Food and Drinks	149	38.7%
Total	385	100%

Based on the table above, it can be seen that almost half of the total number of respondents, which accounted for 41.6% of the total number of respondents, indicated that their nature of business is food only. While on the other hand, 19.7% of the total number of the respondents indicated that their nature of business is only in drinks. However, in terms of both food and drinks, 38.70% of the total number of respondents chose this as the nature of their business.

2. Respondents Assess the Digital Marketing Strategies of Online Food Sellers in terms of:

a. Accuracy of Digital Advertisements

Table 5: Weighted Mean, Standard Deviation, Interpretation, and Ranking Accuracy of Digital Advertisements

Accuracy of Digital Marketing	mean	stdev	interpretation	rank
1. Digital Advertisements online shows exact picture of the product	3.465	0.577	agree	4
2. Shows exact price of product	3.488	0.550	agree	2
3. Quality of the product is the same from actual and online advertisements.	3.405	0.601	agree	5
4. Online promotions are implemented	3.556	0.547	strongly agree	1
5. Description of the product in digital marketing is factual in actual product	3.475	0.586	agree	3
Overall mean	3.478	0.290	Good	

The table 2.1 shows the responses of the responders regarding the Accuracy of Digital Marketing. The respondents strongly agree that the online promotion is implemented with the mean of 3.556 and the standard deviation of 0.547, resulting in rank 1, followed by 2nd in rank, shows exact price with the mean of 3.488 and the 0.550 in standard deviation respondents agree to this. Meanwhile, the description of the product in digital marketing is factual in actual product ranking in 3rd place consisting of the mean 3.475 and 0.586 in standard deviation making the respondents agree to this. The respondents agree that the digital advertisements online shows exact picture of the product with the mean of 3.465 and the standard deviation of 0.577, resulting in rank 4. Lastly, the respondents also agree that the quality of the product is the same from actual and online advertisements with the mean of 3.405 and 0.601 in standard deviation, ranking in 5th place.

In complete data, the overall mean of accuracy of digital marketing has 3.478 in total and 0.290 in standard deviation, resulting in **Good** for its interpretation. According to Maniyani (2022), utilizing accurate intent data is critical to the success of any marketing and sales organization. It helps build the integrity of the brand, shorten the sales cycle and increase revenue. The right intent data acts as a compass that guides you to the right customer at the right time for the solution.

b. Frequency of Digital Advertisements

Table 6: Weighted Mean, Standard Deviation, Interpretation, and Ranking Frequency of Digital Advertisements

Frequency of Digital Advertisements	mean	stdev	Interpretation	rank
1. Advertisements are showing in adequate frequency	3.649	0.494	strongly agree	1
2. New products are being updated in the Digital Marketing Advertisements	3.597	0.532	strongly agree	2
3. Digital Ads are being showed in acceptable manner	3.499	0.526	strongly agree	4
4. Notification of new digital marketing advertisement is acceptable	3.483	0.511	Agree	5

Frequency of Digital Advertisements	mean	stdev	Interpretation	rank
5. Digital Marketing approaches changes frequency	3.514	0.511	strongly agree	3
Overall mean	3.549	0.256	Very good	

The table 2.2 shows the responses of the responders regarding the frequency of digital marketing. The respondents strongly agree that the advertisements are showing in adequate frequency with the mean of 3.649 and the standard deviation of 0.494, resulting in rank 1, followed by 2nd in rank, new products are being updated in the Digital Marketing Advertisements with the mean of 3.597 and the 0.532 in standard deviation respondents strongly agree to this. Meanwhile, the digital marketing approaches changes frequency ranking in 3rd place consisting of the mean 3.514 and 0.511 in standard deviation making the respondents strongly agree to this. The respondents strongly agree that the digital ads are being showed in acceptable manner with the mean of 3.499 and the standard deviation of 0.526, resulting in rank 4. Lastly, the respondents also agree that the notification of new digital marketing advertisement is acceptable with the mean of 3.483 and 0.511 in standard deviation, ranking in 5th place.

In complete data, the overall mean of frequency of digital marketing has 3.549 in total and 0.256 in standard deviation, resulting in **Very Good** for its interpretation. As explained by AlDeghaither (2023), frequency refers to the number of times a person sees an ad. The more often a person sees an ad, the more likely they are to remember it. Frequency is important because it helps advertisers to ensure that their message is being seen enough times to make an impact. A high reach but low frequency may not be effective in generating desired outcomes, while a high frequency but low reach may be a waste of resources. Ideally, advertisers aim for a high reach and high frequency, as this maximizes the chances of the ad making an impact on the target audience.

c. Feedbacks from Previous Customers Help in Decision Buying

Table 7: Weighted Mean, Standard Deviation, Interpretation, and Ranking Feedbacks from Previous Customers Help in Decision Buying

Feedbacks from previous customers	mean	stdev	Interpretation	rank
1. Feedbacks from previous customers helps in decision buying	3.688	0.464	strongly agree	2
2. Feedbacks gives excitement in buying products from the online seller	3.634	0.534	strongly agree	5
3. Feedbacks give truthiness to digital marketing.	3.701	0.458	strongly agree	1
4. Feedbacks changes Digital Marketing approaches	3.649	0.504	strongly agree	4
5. Feedbacks provide initial expectation of the product	3.678	0.530	strongly agree	3
Overall mean	3.670	0.234	Very good	

The table 2.3 shows the responses of the responders regarding the feedbacks from previous customers. The respondents strongly agree that the feedbacks give truthiness to digital marketing. with the mean of 3.701 and the standard deviation of 0.458, resulting in rank 1, followed by 2nd in rank, feedbacks from previous customers helps in decision buying with the mean of 3.688 and the 0.464 in standard deviation respondents strongly agree to this. Meanwhile, Feedbacks provide initial expectation of the product ranking in 3rd place consisting of the mean 3.678 and 0.530 in standard deviation making the respondents strongly agree to this. The respondents agree that feedbacks changes digital marketing approaches with the mean of 3.649 and the standard deviation of 0.504, resulting in rank 4. Lastly, the respondents also strongly agree that Feedbacks gives excitement in buying products from the online seller with the mean of 3.634 and 0.534 in standard deviation, ranking in 5th place.

In complete data, the overall mean of feedbacks from previous customers has 3.670 in total and 0.234 in standard deviation, resulting in **Very Good** for its interpretation. Based on Fieldroutes (2023), customer feedback is a core aspect of the field service business. The ultra-competitive service-based businesses means feedback from customers could be the difference that sets you apart from competitors in the industry. Soliciting and collecting customer feedback highlights areas of improvement and demonstrates the commitment to providing exceptional service.

d. Online Recommendation from Previous Customers

Table 8: Weighted Mean, Standard Deviation, Interpretation, and Ranking Online Recommendation from Previous Customers

Online recommendation from previous customers	mean	stdev	Interpretation	rank
1. Recommendations gives idea that the product’s quality is adequate as shown on digital marketing	3.610	0.499	strongly agree	2
2. Digital Recommendations provides the expectation that digital marketing is giving customers proper information about the products.	3.543	0.529	strongly agree	3
3. Recommendations in social media gives curiosity to customers to try products recommended by other customers	3.447	0.571	Agree	5
4. Recommendations allows customer to consider buying products from the business with digital marketing strategy	3.657	0.486	strongly agree	1
5. Digital recommendations boost digital marketing strategy effectiveness	3.481	0.516	Agree	4
Overall mean	3.548	0.245	Very good	

The table 2.4 shows the responses of the responders regarding the online recommendation from previous customers. The respondents strongly agree that the recommendations allows customer to consider buying products from the business with digital marketing strategy with the mean of 3.657 and the standard deviation of 0.486, resulting in rank 1, followed by 2nd in rank, recommendations gives idea that the product’s quality is adequate as shown on digital marketing with the mean of 3.610 and the 0.499 in standard deviation respondents strongly agree to this. Meanwhile, the digital recommendations provides the expectation that digital marketing is giving customers proper information about the products ranking in 3rd place consisting of the mean 3.543 and 0.529 in standard deviation making the respondents strongly agree to this. The respondents agree that the digital recommendations boost digital marketing strategy effectiveness with the mean of 3.481 and the standard deviation of 0.516, resulting in rank 4. Lastly, the respondents also agree that the recommendations in social media gives curiosity to customers to try products recommended by other customers with the mean of 3.447 and 0.571 in standard deviation, ranking in 5th place.

In complete data, the overall mean of online recommendation from previous customers has 3.548 in total and 0.245 in standard deviation, resulting in **Very Good** for its interpretation. As explained by Indeed Editorial Team (2023), customer reviews can affect the company’s reputation and the public perception of the products or services, business practices or customer service. Having many positive reviews can improve the company's social credibility and leave positive impressions on potential customers. Good reviews allow potential customers to trust the business and feel comfortable making a purchase from you because they know others have had pleasant experiences doing so.

e. Popularity of Digital Advertisements or Pages

Table 9: Weighted Mean, Standard Deviation, Interpretation, and Ranking Popularity of Digital Advertisements or Pages

Popularity of Digital Advertisements or Pages	mean	stdev	Interpretation	rank
1. Gives curiousness from the product an online seller is selling	3.377	0.521	Agree	5
2. Gives consideration in buying products	3.626	0.500	strongly agree	1
3. Make customer buy products from online food seller	3.478	0.526	Agree	4
4. Gives customer excitement to buy products from online food seller	3.579	0.520	strongly agree	2
5. Allows customer to expect adequate quality products from online food seller	3.514	0.526	strongly agree	3
Overall mean	3.515	0.253	Very good	

The table 2.5 shows the responses of the responders regarding popularity of digital advertisements or pages. The respondents strongly agree about gives consideration in buying products, with the mean of 3.626 and the standard deviation of 0.500, resulting in rank 1, followed by 2nd in rank, gives customer excitement to buy products from online food seller with the mean of 3.579 and the 0.520 in standard deviation respondents strongly agree to this. Meanwhile, Allows customer to expect adequate quality products from online food seller ranking in 3rd place consisting of the mean 3.514 and 0.526 in standard deviation making the respondents strongly agree to this. The respondents agree that Make customer buy products from online food seller with the mean of 3.478 and the standard deviation of 0.526, resulting in rank 4. Lastly, the respondents also agree that gives curiousness from the product an online seller is selling with the mean of 3.377 and 0.521 in standard deviation, ranking in 5th place.

In complete data, the overall mean of popularity of digital advertisements or pages has 3.515 in total and 0.253 in standard deviation, resulting in **Very Good** for its interpretation. As indicated in Google for Small Businesses, online advertising allows you to find, reach, and engage people who are likely to be interested in the business without spending money on an overly broad audience. Online advertising offers granular audience information, so you can focus the efforts effectively.

3. Significant difference on the respondents assessments on the digital marketing strategies of Online Food Sellers when grouped according to:

a. Age

Comparison of the respondents assessments on the digital marketing strategies of Online Food Sellers when grouped according to Age.

Table 10

Age	mean	Stdev	f-comp	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
20 yrs old and below	3.5563	.10025	1.109	.352	failed to reject Ho	no significant difference
21 - 30 years old	3.5500	.14938				
31 - 40 years old	3.5419	.10334				
41 - 50 years old	3.6033	.09130				
51 years old and above	3.5000	.02828				

Analysis of Variance was used to check if the difference exists in the considered group, from the table above it can be seen that f-comp value is 1.109 with a p-value of 0.352 which is higher than the 5% level of significance. The hypothesis that

there is no significant difference on the respondents assessments on the digital marketing strategies of Online Food Sellers when grouped according to age is **Accepted**. This implies that different age groups of the respondents **do not differ** on their assessments on the digital marketing strategies of Online Food Sellers. They all do agree that the digital strategies of online food sellers is very good as reflected in the mean response for each group.

b. Nature of Business

Comparison of the respondents assessments on the digital marketing strategies of Online Food Sellers when grouped according to Nature of Business

Table 11

Nature of Business	mean	Stdev	f-comp	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Drinks only	3.5474	.12224	4.274	.015	reject Ho	There is a significant difference
Food only	3.5740	.11803				
Food and Drinks	3.5302	.15069				

Analysis of Variance was used to check if the difference exist on the considered group, from the table above it can be seen that f-comp value is 4.274 with a p-value of 0.015 which is lower than the 5% level of significance. The hypothesis that there is no significant difference on the respondents assessments on the digital marketing strategies of Online Food Sellers when grouped according to the nature of business is **Rejected**. This implies that the different nature of business of the respondents **differ** on their assessments on the digital marketing strategies of Online Food Sellers. Although they all do agree that the digital strategies of online food sellers is very good as reflected in the mean response for each group, you can also notice that it is the Food only business that has the highest mean and with a lowest standard deviation.

4. Enhanced digital marketing strategy for Online Food Sellers can be proposed based on the respondent’s assessments.

To successfully launch a digital business, they must conduct in-depth market research to identify their target audience, their interests, and behavior. Online Food Sellers should also have the need to analyze their competitors to identify market opportunities and points of uniqueness. Setting precise, measurable goals for their digital marketing initiatives, such as increasing website traffic, improving conversion rates, or expanding the customer base you service, is one tactic for building the business. Creating a user-friendly, visually appealing website that has a focus on food photography and captivating descriptions. Selecting the social media platforms that the target market uses the most. Additionally, They may target their ideal clients with paid advertising on websites like Google Ads and social media, and they can encourage them to make purchases and provide reviews and feedback on their website and social media pages. Furthermore, respond quickly to any criticism and use favorable comments as testimonials. Utilize user feedback and rankings to win over prospective clients.

A strategy should be flexible and fluid. To increase the performance and consumer satisfaction of the online food selling business, keep an eye on the outcomes, gather client feedback, and be prepared to make adjustments as necessary. Online food sellers should develop a more effective digital marketing plan that is customized to their industry and their demands.

V. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This chapter deals with a summary of findings, conclusions, and recommendations of the research study.

This study aims to provide a summary of the findings and conclusions that were derived from the results of the survey that were conducted. The survey was conducted online on a purposive sampling of 385 respondents within IV-A CALABARZON region and in NCR region using research-made questionnaires.

A. Summary of Findings

The following are the findings of the study as they correspond to the stated problems:

1. The Demographic Profile of the Respondents based on Age, Gender, Place of Business, and Nature of Business.

Age. 62.6% of respondents were 21 - 30 years old, according to the statistics. 22.3% of respondents came from 31 - 40 years old. 8.3% were aged 20 years old and below. 6.2 of respondents 41 - 50 years old followed. Ages from 51 years old and above consisting of 0.5% had the fewest respondents.

Gender. The majority of the respondents were Females with a total of 256 or 66.5% while male respondents totaled 129 or 33.5%.

Place of Business. Most of the respondents' locations were within IV-A CALABARZON region with a total of 230 or 59.7%, while in NCR region with a total of 155 or 40.3% of respondents.

Nature of Business. The majority of respondents were from the business of Food only with a total of 160 or 41.6%, followed by both Food and Drinks with 149 or 38.7%, and drinks only for 76 or 19.7% of the respondents.

2. Respondents assess the digital marketing strategies of Online Food Sellers in terms of:

a. Accuracy of Digital Marketing

As shown by respondents' responses to the accuracy of Digital Marketing, the online promotion are implemented ranked 1st responded Strongly Agree, while showing exact price ranked 2nd responded Agree, followed by Description of the product in digital marketing is factual in actual product ranked 3rd responded Agree. Next is Digital Advertisements online shows exact picture of the product ranked 4th responded Agree, and Quality of the product is the same from actual and online advertisements ranked 5th or last responded Agree.

b. Frequency of Digital Advertisements

As shown by respondents' response to the Frequency of Digital Advertisements, the advertisements are showing in adequate frequency ranked 1st responded Strongly Agree, while the new products are being updated in the digital marketing advertisements ranked 2nd responded Strongly Agree, followed by digital marketing approaches changes frequency ranked 3rd responded Strongly Agree. Next is digital ads are being shown in an acceptable manner ranked 4th responded Strongly Agree. Lastly, notification of new digital marketing advertisement is acceptable ranked 5th responded Agree.

c. Feedbacks from previous customers help in decision buying.

As shown by respondents' response to the Feedbacks from previous customers help in decision buying, feedbacks give truthiness to digital marketing ranked 1st responded Strongly Agree, while feedbacks from previous customers helps in decision buying ranked 2nd responded Strongly Agree, followed by feedbacks provide initial expectation of the product ranked 3rd responded Strongly Agree. Next is feedback changes digital marketing approaches ranked 4th and lastly, feedback gives excitement in buying products from the online seller ranked 5th responded Strongly Agree.

d. Online Recommendation from Previous Customers

As shown by respondents' response to the Online Recommendation from Previous Customers, recommendations allows customer to consider buying products from the business with digital marketing strategy ranked 1st responded Strongly Agree, while recommendations gives idea that the product's quality is adequate as shown on digital marketing ranked 2nd responded Strongly Agree, followed by Digital Recommendations provides the expectation that digital marketing is giving customer proper information about the products ranked 3rd responded Strongly Agree. Next is digital recommendations boost digital marketing strategy effectiveness ranked 4th responded Agree and lastly, recommendations in social media gives curiosity to customers to try products recommended by other customers ranked 5th responded Agree.

e. Popularity of Digital Advertisements or Pages

As shown by respondents' response to the Popularity of Digital Advertisements or Pages, giving consideration in buying products ranked 1st responded Strongly Agree, while Giving customer excitement to buy products from online seller ranked 2nd responded Strongly Agree, followed by allowing customer to expect adequate quality products from online food seller ranked 3rd responded Strongly Agree. Next is making customers buy products from online food sellers ranked 4th responding only Agree and lastly, giving curiosity from the product an online seller is selling ranked 5th responded only Agree.

3. Significant difference on the respondents assessments on the digital marketing strategies of Online Food Sellers when grouped according to:

a. Age

Within the considered group of age, the collected data can be seen that f-comp value is 1.109 with a p-value of 0.352 which is higher than the 5% level of significance. When respondents are classified by age, there is no discernible variation in their opinions of the digital marketing tactics used by online food sellers. This suggests that opinions among respondents of

different ages on the online food sellers' digital marketing tactics are similar. According to the mean response for each group, they all agree that the digital strategies used by online food sellers are excellent.

b. Nature of Business

Within the considered group, the collected data can be seen that f-comp value is 4.274 with a p-value of 0.015 which is lower than the 5% level of significance. When grouped by the type of business, there is no apparent variation in the respondents' evaluations of the online food sellers' digital marketing strategies, which are Rejected. This suggests that the respondents' various line of work affects how they evaluate the online food sellers' digital marketing strategies. Although the mean responses for each group show that they all concur that the digital methods of online food sellers are excellent.

4. Enhanced digital marketing strategy for Online Food Sellers can be proposed based on the respondent's assessments.

In-depth market research is essential to setting up a profitable digital food business, including defining the target market and examining rivals. Digital marketing strategies should have goals that are specific and measurable. Utilizing well-known social media platforms and creating a visually appealing website with a focus on food portrayal are crucial. Targeting ideal customers with paid advertising is possible, and it's critical to value customer feedback and reviews. The approach should continue to be adaptable, including consumer feedback to raise performance and satisfaction. The secret to success is tailoring the digital marketing strategy to the unique requirements of the online food selling business.

B. Conclusion

Given the findings conducted by the researcher, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. The Demographic Profile of the Respondents based on Age, Gender, Place of Business, and Nature of Business.

The majority of respondents are dominated by females with the age of 21 - 30 years old and most of their places of business are situated within the IV-A CALABARZON region, and as per their nature of work, their online business is governed by food only.

2. Respondents assess the digital marketing strategies of Online Food Sellers in terms of:

a. Accuracy of Digital Marketing

According to the data provided, all remarks given to respondents were rated significant. Overall, respondents agree (3.478) that the accuracy of digital marketing is **Good** and can be implemented through online promotions, showing exact price, giving factual description of product, showing exact picture, and giving the assurance of the quality of the product in advertisements.

b. Frequency of Digital Advertisements

All statements supplied to respondents had an overall mean of 3.549, indicating strong significance. Respondents strongly agree that the implementation of frequency of digital marketing is **Very Good** to execute through advertisements showing adequate frequency, new products being updated in digital ads, digital marketing changes frequency, digital ads showing in acceptable manner, and getting notification of new digital marketing ads.

c. Feedbacks from previous customers help in decision buying.

As stated by the collected data, all the respondents strongly agree with the overall mean of 3.670 that the feedback from previous customers help in decision buying is Very Good and can be executed and considered.

d. Online Recommendation from Previous Customers

In relation to the collected data, all respondents strongly agree with the overall mean of 3.548 that online recommendations from previous customers is Very Good and can be carried through implementing a more well verse digital marketing strategy.

e. Popularity of Digital Advertisements or Pages

In accordance with the collected data, the respondents strongly agree with an overall mean of 3.515 that popularity of digital advertisements or pages is **Very Good** and can be implemented and considered.

3. Significant difference on the respondents assessments on the digital marketing strategies of Online Food Sellers when grouped according to:

a. Age

There is no noticeable difference in the opinions of respondents on the digital marketing strategies utilized by online food suppliers when respondents are categorized by age. This implies that attitudes on the digital marketing strategies used by online food suppliers are consistent across respondents of various ages.

b. Nature of Business

The respondents' varied professional backgrounds have an impact on how they assess the digital marketing tactics used by online food vendors. Nevertheless, it is clear from the average responses for each group that they all think the digital methods used by online food sellers are preferable.

4. Enhanced digital marketing strategy for Online Food Sellers can be proposed based on the respondent's assessments.

Online food sellers can be proactive and make the required adjustments to their digital marketing strategy with this information at their disposal. Being flexible enables them to keep one step ahead of the competition and meet the changing needs of their target market.

C. Recommendations

Based from the prior conclusions, the following recommendations are developed:

1. The respondents' assessment of the digital marketing strategies of online food sellers in terms of accuracy of digital marketing, frequency of digital marketing, feedback from previous customers help in decision buying, online recommendation from previous customers, and popularity of digital advertisements or pages should be imploded and consider in market research, analytics, data tracking, and overall performance of the business.
2. Online food businesses can enhance the digital marketing strategy proposed by the respondents assessment by flexible information they will get. Enhancing the social media marketing, online advertisement, content and email marketing, and website optimization.
3. Future researchers can use this study as a guide to expand their research and come up with a unified and reliable conclusion.

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